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Nurturing Creative Engineering Graduates By Embedding Creativity Heuristics Into Existing Subjects

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INTRODUCTION. CREATIVITY: THE ENGINEERING EDUCATORS CHALLENGE

Over 50 years ago Olken [1] reflected on the importance of creativity training for engineers and inability of engineering education to nurture creative graduates:

“If our inventors of the future are to have the higher analytical abilities needed to cope with our increasingly technical inventions, the present overemphasis or unbalance of analytical training relative to training in creativity will increase even more rapidly than our present creativity training courses will be able to correct it. We will therefore need much greater development and expansion of creativity training in engineering schools than are now planned, merely to keep the imbalance at its present level. In short, as far as the future is concerned in creativity training of engineers, we will have to run much faster just to stand still.” [1].

It seems that development of creative graduates still represents a significant challenge for engineering education in many countries. The following are some recent examples from Europe, Australia and North America that evidence the need for engineering educators to improve creativity training.

Gaudron and Kövesi [2] recently analysed opinions of French engineering students on the skills they would need to possess to innovate as well as students' perceptions on gaining these skills while studying engineering. The biggest disagreement between the importance of the skill and the successful acquisition of that skill at university was discovered for the creativity skills (4.2 versus 1.7; on the Likert scale of 5, with 1 corresponding to complete disagreement and 5 – to complete agreement) [2]. Valentine, Belski, and Hamilton [3] discovered that Australian engineering curricula devote very little space to nurturing creative problem solving skills. Only 20 subject outlines of 919 core subjects that were taught by 34

electrical/electronics programs explicitly stated that some concepts of creativity and/or innovation are mentioned or taught to students. Marquis, Radan, and Liu [4], who evaluated the degree of teaching creativity by analysing outlines of 1184 subjects taught by five faculties at a Canadian university, found that only 1 of the 149 subject outlines from engineering faculty mentioned creativity. Daly, Mosyjowski, & Seifert [5] scrutinised syllabuses of seven engineering subjects from a public university in the United States of America and found that all the seven subjects were focused on skills of reorganising, analysing and evaluation and had significant gaps in instruction on creative skills.

It would be incorrect to generalise the findings of scholars from France, Australia, Canada and USA and to conclude that the situation with nurturing creativity in future engineers is poor at all educational institutions. There are some reports of successes in creativity training [6-9], but these successes seem to represent exceptions in development of creativity by engineering educators, rather than the rule.

In essence, the findings of Valentine et al [3], Gaudron and Kövesi [2], Marquis et al. [4] and Daly et al. [5] demonstrate that the abovementioned Olken's reflection is as relevant today as it was 54 years ago. The challenges of educating creative engineers have not been yet resolved and are still on the agenda of engineering educators.

1 ENGINEERING CREATIVITY

In order to improve creativity skills it is necessary to define creativity and to establish the criteria to measure the improvement in creativity skills. Scholars have been interested in sources of creativity and the ways to enhance it for centuries. The domain of human creativity has been extensively researched for over 100 years. Nonetheless, the researchers have neither agreed on the definition of creativity nor on the proper methodologies to measure it [10, 11]. Some scholars suggested that creativity means different things in different domains [12, 13] and argued that the definitions and the means to measure creativity need to be domain specific [14].

Taking into account recent findings on domain specificity of creativity skills, this paper will use the definition of creativity developed specifically for engineering, the definition that took into account legal aspects of patentability and patent authorship:

“Engineering creativity is the ability to generate novel solution ideas for open-ended problems, ideas that are not obvious to experts in a particular engineering discipline and that are considered by them as potentially useful”. [15]

This definition of creativity suggests that in order to enhance students' creativity it is required to boost their *ability to generate novel ideas* to open-ended problems. One of the ways to develop this ability is to introduce students to effective thinking heuristics. Actually, the successes in creativity training of engineering students mentioned in the previous section of this paper were achieved as a result of teaching students various creativity heuristics. Also, the importance of heuristics for generating novel ideas has been considered as essential by creativity scholars for over three decades [16]. Let us establish thinking heuristics that can facilitate generation of novel design ideas.

2 HEURISTICS FOR CREATIVE ENGINEERING DESIGN

2.1 'Creative' Stages of Engineering Design

Engineers need creativity skills to design novel artefacts and to improve existing systems. Consequently, to establish how to enhance students' abilities to generate novel ideas and what thinking heuristics to teach, it is necessary to determine which stages of engineering design are the most critical in formation of novel ideas.

Howard, Culley, & Dekoninck [17] considered over 20 models of engineering design process and nearly 20 models of creative process and mapped the creative process onto design process. They concluded that in practice creative output occurs mainly during stages of task analysis and idea generation.

Although the importance of the design stage of idea generation for attaining creative ideas is self-evident, it appears that the stage of task analysis, which is also known as problem finding, problem framing, situation/problem analysis, etc., is equally important for attaining creative solutions. The essential role of the problem finding stage for developing creative artefacts had been recognised by many researchers that explored the winning approaches of famous design innovators and engineering experts [18-21]. Therefore, in order to select the heuristics that can aid in creativity training of engineers, it is necessary to establish thinking heuristics that can help engineers in accomplishing the design stages of task analysis and idea generation.

2.2 Thinking Heuristics for Task Analysis

Numerous scholars discovered that both students and professionals effectively generate innovative ideas during the stage of problem finding with help of simple thinking heuristics. Famous design innovators, for example, framed their problems by means of the following activities: (a) by altering the initial constraint set [20]; (b) by reassessing the problem from first principles [18]; (c) by re-evaluating the product's application; (d) by identifying the key question to be addressed [22]; (e) by immersing in the problem situation, studying it in depth and reflecting [19, 23]; and (f) by changing the focus of task analysis from the systems level to the level of individual elements and then back [19]. A recent case study reported that a simple TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) heuristic of Situation Analysis that was used by engineers to frame a problem was imperative for development of an innovative crash barrier that was patented and also won a government tender [24].

As expert engineers, students can also boost their creativity using thinking heuristics during problem framing. For example, a simple heuristic known as TERISSA (Task Evaluation and Reflection Instrument for Student Self-Assessment) that engaged students in evaluating a complexity of a problem before and after solving it helped students in problem analysis and engaged them in meaningful self-reflection [25].

Recent Australian study revealed that creativity skills can be taught effectively by embedding learning of simple thinking heuristic into existing discipline subjects.

One hundred and ten students who were enrolled in the first year subject of Engineering Materials at Swinburne University of Technology participated in the study of Blicblau and Ang [26]. During one of the subject laboratories that was conducted in a blended learning mode (no face-to-face contact with laboratory tutors), students were asked to select materials to build various engineering structures, like bridges, homes or hand tools. After students made their decisions on the materials for manufacturing the structures, they were asked to learn the heuristic

of Size-Time-Cost (STC) Operator and to repeat the exercise of material selection. The Size-Time-Cost Operator heuristic suggests to ponder on the changes to the problematic situation under six (unreachable) conditions: when the *Size* of the problematic issue is either infinite (1) or zero (2); when the *Time* to improve the situation is either infinite (3) or zero (4); when the *Cost* of the improvement is either infinite (5) or zero (6).

Blicblau and Ang reported significant differences in choices of materials made by the students which could only be explained by the use of the Size-Time-Cost Operator heuristic:

When students responded to the first engineering activity for realistic solutions to the materials selection problems, they all selected either one of two classes of materials for the engineering components, i.e. metals (e.g. varieties of steel, aluminium, or composites)... When students were asked to... [use] the TRIZ (STC) approach... a variety of traditional (steel, aluminium and wood) and non-traditional materials (titanium, carbon nanotubes, graphene, diamond, ceramics, and gold) were selected for the various constraints. [26]

Blicblau and Ang concluded that the STC Operator heuristic helped students to remove the constraints related to traditional engineering techniques and to consider novel materials and novel manufacturing techniques. In essence, a simple heuristic of Size-Time-Cost Operator that was 'embedded' into an existing laboratory exercise, helped students to expand their view on the materials available to manufacture various structures.

It is important to note that, although the application of the STC Operator heuristic was not compulsory and did not influence the laboratory mark, the majority of students enrolled in the materials course used the heuristic and were enthusiastic about the outcomes it helped them to produce.

2.3 Thinking Heuristics for Idea Generation

The ability of thinking heuristics to aid in idea generation has been evidenced by numerous findings from industry and academia. Scholars of engineering creativity that studied the methods used by famous designers discovered that some great designers even developed their own heuristics to attained winning ideas. The following are some examples of these practical methods: (a) engage in mental transfer of technology from one application to another [23], (b) identify analogies between the problem and various other products with similar functionality [23], (iii) formulate the Ideal Ultimate Result and reflect on the reasons that obstruct its achievement [24].

The ability of the TRIZ heuristic of the Eight Fields of MATCEMIB to trigger novel ideas has been supported by numerous experiments that involved over 1,500 engineering students from six countries. It was found that this simple heuristic statistically significantly increased the number of diverse ideas proposed by subjects for an open-ended problem [27-29]. Daly, Yilmaz, Christian, Seifert and Gonzalez [30] reported that a number of design (thinking) heuristics helped engineering students to propose more ideas for their projects.

Another recent study used the educational materials of the TRIZ Repository [31] that was developed with the support of the Australian Government Department of Education and Training. This Repository offers its users four kinds of resources: educational materials for self-learning, educational materials for academic use,

research papers and case studies on the application of TRIZ heuristics. TRIZ Repository was developed in order to allow subject coordinators to embed one or two heuristics into existing courses with minimal effort on their part. Educational materials on all heuristics contain short introductory videos, simple solution templates and cheat sheets that can be used by individual students in and out of class.

Sixty students enrolled in various diploma programs at the Toi-Ohomai Institute of Technology (TOIT) in New Zealand were introduced to three TRIZ heuristics in semester 1 of 2017 [32]. Students were a mix of school leavers and mature age students and represented both first-year and second-year (graduating) student cohorts. Three class sessions to introduce TRIZ heuristics of the Eight Fields of MATCEMIB, the Ideal Ultimate Result (IUR) and the Size-Time-Cost Operator were conducted. This was done in accordance with the recommendations provided by the TRIZ Repository [31].

The Eight Fields of MATCEMIB heuristic is a subset of the TRIZ tool of Substance-Field Analysis [33]. It recommends for a user to consider solutions that are based on eight different principles of operation: Mechanical, Acoustic, Thermal, Chemical, Electric, Magnetic, Intermolecular and Biological (MATCEMIB). A number of experiments conducted internationally showed that this heuristic can help students to statistically significantly increase the number and the breadth of ideas generated for solving an open-ended problem [e.g.29]. The IUR heuristic suggests for a practitioner to formulate the Ideal Ultimate Result for the problematic situation (the problem has to resolve itself) and to reflect on the reasons why the IUR is not achievable [34].

Twenty-one TOIT students participated in a web-based survey that was conducted a few months after they had been introduced to the TRIZ heuristics in class. Most of the survey participants confirmed that they had devoted their own time and studied more TRIZ heuristics from the TRIZ Repository on their own and agreed that TRIZ heuristics helped them to generate more novel ideas. *Table 1* depicts student opinions on the influence of heuristics presented in [32].

Table 1. Student opinions on the influence of TRIZ heuristics. All questions used the Likert scale of 5 (1 – strongly disagree; 5 – strongly agree) [32]

	I believe the heuristic(s) I have learnt helped me to understand my problem much more clearly	I believe the heuristic(s) I have learnt helped me to generate more ideas for my project	Learning the heuristics changed a way I resolve problems
Mean	4.00	4.06	3.87
SD	0.365	0.443	0.500

Students also assessed the usefulness of the educational materials provided by the Repository as fully suitable for self-learning and useful in their future career [32]. Furthermore, four graduating students had actually incorporated the outcomes of their application of the TRIZ heuristics into their final project reports.

3 DISCUSSION

It is hard to disagree with creativity scholars and engineering experts on the value of thinking heuristics for problem analysis and idea generation. Years of research and hundreds of novel designs have verified that application of thinking heuristics can positively influence the outcome of engineering work.

Accepting the importance of thinking heuristics and taking into account successes of educators from Swinburne University of Technology and Toi-Ohomai Institute of Technology in embedding them into existing subject, a conclusion can be reached that embedding effective creativity heuristics into existing engineering subjects may help educators to improve the situation with development of students' creativity. It can be argued, though, that engaging engineering students for just one hour to learn a heuristic may not result in a long-term improvement of creativity skills. It is possible that the improvement in problem framing and idea generation that students experienced directly after they were introduced to thinking heuristics in class may not last and may not transfer to long-term improvement of creativity skills. This scenario is certainly viable, however, the outcomes of the experiment conducted by Valentine, Belski, & Hamilton [35] suggest that long-term retention of the heuristic approach by students who were engaged in one-hour 'training' session is likely. Eleven weeks after being exposed to the Eight Fields of MATCEMIB heuristic for 30 minutes during tutorial, students were able to generate statistically significantly more ideas for an open-ended problem compared to students who have not been introduced to the Eight Fields of MATCEMIB heuristic [35].

At the same time, the successes in embedding simple TRIZ heuristics of Size-Time Cost Operator, the Eight Fields of MATCEMIB and the Ideal Ultimate Result presented in [26, 32] cannot be considered as the final confirmation that any simple thinking heuristic can be embedded in any existing subject and will enhance students' creativity skills. Educators need to choose subjects that suit creativity development and also select heuristics to teach that are the most adequate for a specific subject.

This paper has devoted most of its space to thinking heuristics of TRIZ. This does not mean that other thinking heuristics cannot enhance problem framing and idea generation. Heuristics of TRIZ were considered because they specifically were developed for engineering and therefore suit engineering well.

4 CONCLUSION

The challenges faced by engineering educators are growing. Discipline knowledge expands exponentially; engineering companies request graduates with well-developed 'soft' skills (team work, presentation, cognitive, etc.). It is practically impossible to devote a separate subject specifically to development of creativity skills with already extremely busy engineering curriculum. Some novel approaches to instill creativity into engineering students are required. The successes of simple heuristics in enabling both experts and novices to propose more novel ideas suggest that it would be advantageous to teach thinking heuristics at engineering schools. Moreover, the existing evidence of successes in teaching simple thinking heuristics to engineering students as well as availability of educational resources may enable many engineering educators to embed simple thinking heuristics for problem analysis and idea generation into existing discipline subjects.

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